

**Ocean Cryosphere Exchanges in Antarctica:
Impacts on Climate and the Earth System**

Deliverable D4.2 Uncertainty results integrated into UKESM

Milestone MS13

**Funded by
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**UK Research
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UK Partners are funded by UK Research and Innovation (UKRI) under the UK government's Horizon Europe funding Guarantee.

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Milestone report

Work Packages	WP6 Role of Antarctica in the global climate: long-term impacts of short-term decision-making
Milestone no. & title	MS13 Deliverable D4.2 uncertainty results integrated into UKESM
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Version	Final
Due date	31 March 2026
Delivery date	20 April 2026

Cover sheet: Photo by Anna Olive Abello.

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1. Means of verification of the achievement of the milestone

This milestone links the research performed in Work Packages 4, “Quantification of Antarctic Ice Sheet deep uncertainty and freshwater fluxes under climate forcing” and 6, “Role of Antarctica in the global climate: long-term impacts of short-term decision-making”. WP4 uses ice sheet models (ISMs) to constrain the freshwater fluxes produced during the future retreat of the Antarctic ice sheet (AIS). This was done using a large ensemble of experiments in which climate forcing is prescribed and details of the ice sheet model varied. In this way, a probabilistic prediction was created. In contrast, the projections of WP6 use a fully coupled Earth system model (ESM), which has the advantage of including feedbacks between the ice sheet and the wider climate system that may affect future freshwater release (which are largely absent in WP4’s approach). The disadvantage is that ESMs are computationally demanding, and only very few experiments are possible. In WP6’s ESM experiments, retreat of the AIS is spontaneously triggered by changes in the coastal waters surrounding Antarctica. The aim of the milestone is to use WP4 results to provide a wider context for this retreat. This is done by comparing the time series of freshwater release in the ESM with the range of freshwater-release scenarios produced in WP4.

2. Work performed and main achievements

2.1 Description of work

WP6 employs the UKESM Earth system model to make projections of future climate. UKESM is one of the very few IPCC-class ESMs that include interactive coupling with both the Greenland and Antarctic ice sheets. This UKESM configuration is described in Smith et al. (2021) and Siahann et al. (2022). In the experiments reported here, UKESM is forced in an idealised manner using a constant rate of anthropogenic CO₂ emissions. These specific experiments are described in detail by Smith et al. (2026). The global warming produced by these CO₂ emissions triggers changes in the regional ocean circulation around AIS such that relatively warm ocean waters enter cavities under Antarctica’s largest ice shelves (the Ross and Filchner-Ronne). These warm water masses increase the amount of melt experienced by the ice shelves, leading to ice sheet retreat and a dramatic increase in freshwater entering the Southern Ocean. Elsewhere in WP6, the impact of these freshwater fluxes on regional and global climate is assessed. The number of UKESM experiments that can be performed is severely limited by the model’s very high computational demands. It is therefore difficult to assign a probability to the magnitude of freshwater release in UKESM and, therefore, also to its impact on global and regional climate.

In contrast, WP4 uses the KORI-ULB ice sheet model to produce a historically calibrated ensemble of future freshwater release from AIS using forcing from a range of ESMs to 2300 for the SSP585 emission scenario. This research is reported in Coulon et al. (2024) and allows a probabilistic assessment of the magnitude of future freshwater release. Placing UKESM results in the wider context given by the KORI-ULB ensemble provides a method of assessing the likelihood of the climate impacts observed in UKESM. For instance, if the magnitude of freshwater release in UKESM were to lie far above the KORI-ULB ensemble, we might attach a low likelihood to the projected impacts (and vice versa).

Figure 1 shows results from this comparison for freshwater release from the entire ice sheet. Three modes of freshwater release are displayed: snow and ice surface melt with subsequent runoff to the ocean; melt from the underside of floating ice shelves directly to the ocean; and the melt of icebergs produced by the

ice sheet. The KORI-ULB ensemble is shown in grey for the SSP585 emission scenario, while two UKESM experiments are shown: one in which the AIS is allowed to respond to climate change within the ESM (red) and one in which its geometry is held fixed (blue). Jing et al. (in prep.) analyse the differences between these two experiments and show that the fixed AIS geometry experiment releases more freshwater because the stabilising feedback of a shoaling, flattening ice shelf is omitted.

The emissions forcings (and hence the rate of global warming) used by UKESM (a constant rate of 8 GtC yr^{-1} equivalent to a $2 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ increase in global mean temperature per century) and KORI-ULB ensemble (SSP585) are different so that a correction is required to make this comparison, which takes the form of a simple offset in time between years 10-50 of the UKESM simulation and 1975-2025 of the KORI-ULB simulations.

In general, the freshwater fluxes simulated within UKESM are consistent with those of the KORI-ULB ensemble. For the largest flux of ice-shelf melt ('basal mass loss'), projected UKESM fluxes fall well within the KORI-ULB ensemble; however, the peak occurs somewhat later by as much as 150 years, most likely reflecting differences in the parameterisation of ice shelf melt and processes leading to the ingress of warm water into ice shelf cavities. For runoff ('friver'), they fall close to the lower limit of the ensemble, perhaps reflecting differences in the model used to calculate surface melt (day-degrees in KORI-ULB compared to an energy-balance model in UKESM). Finally, iceberg melt ('ficeberg') is also consistent, although UKESM is somewhat low, most likely because the UKESM ice sheet model lacks an active iceberg calving model (simply losing mass from the ice front at the rate that it is affected to that front).

Fig. 1: Freshwater fluxes (Gt yr^{-1}) from UKESM and KORI-ULB. The KORI-ULB ensemble's SSP585 5-95% probability range is represented by the grey envelope, while two UKESM experiments are shown in blue (ice sheet geometry held constant) and red (fully interactive). The three panels show: surface melt and subsequent runoff (left), ice shelf melt (middle), and iceberg calving and subsequent melt (right).

In summary, this analysis suggests that the freshwater released in UKESM is consistent with the far broader uncertainty analysis of WP4, although somewhat on the low side with a delayed peak. This implies that any global and regional impacts found in the UKESM simulations can be linked to OCEAN ICE's projections of future freshwater release to the oceans.

2.2 References

V. Coulon et al. (2024) Future freshwater fluxes from the Antarctic ice sheet, *Geophysical Research Letters*, 51, e2024GL111250, <https://doi.org/10.1029/2024GL111250>

J. Jing, et al. (*in prep.*) Geometric feedback on Antarctic ice shelf melting, *The Cryosphere*.

A. Siahhan et al. (2022), The Antarctic contribution to 21st century sea-level rise predicted by the UK Earth System Model with an interactive ice sheet, *The Cryosphere*, 16(10), 4053-4086, ISSN 1994-0424, doi: [10.5194/tc-16-4053-2022](https://doi.org/10.5194/tc-16-4053-2022)

R. Smith et al. (2021), Coupling the U.K. Earth System Model to dynamic models of the Greenland and Antarctic ice sheets, *Journal of Advances in Modelling Earth Systems*, 13(10), e2021MS002520. ISSN 1942-2466 doi: [10.1029/2021MS002520](https://doi.org/10.1029/2021MS002520)

R. Smith et al. (2025), Response of ice sheets, sea-ice and sea level in climate stabilisation and reversibility simulations using a state-of-the-art Earth System Model, *EGUsphere* [preprint], <https://doi.org/10.5194/egusphere-2025-4476>

2.3 Open Science

Peer-reviewed publications

An open-access publication is in preparation that will include, in part, this analysis. The authors will select a CC BY licence or equivalent. There will not be any embargo period.

The authors will deposit the Version of Record or the Author Accepted Manuscript in a trusted repository approved by the publisher under a CC BY (or equivalent) licence, as required by Horizon Europe.

Dataset

Data from the KORI-ULB ensemble is available on Zenodo: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14162775>